

Deleted: SEIFU TADESSE

RESPONSE PAPER

LAST NAME: Debalke

FIRST NAME: Seifu Tadesse

PROGRAM CODE: DIPH

COURSE CODE: ACA-401D

PERIOD NUMBER: 1

INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma

Deleted:

Deleted: ☒

Deleted:

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied U.S. U.K. conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did not use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did did not use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: Microsoft Word 365 on Windows 10

List your 5 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. The Basics of Essay Writing (EUCLID 2021, 1-4)
2. Organizing Your Idea (EUCLID 2021, 2)
3. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 5-13)
4. Style Guide (EUCLID 2021, 24-26)
5. Rule of Thumb for Academic Writing (EUCLID 2021, 14-16)

BASICS OF ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

Formatted: RP Title, Border: Bottom: (No border)

1) INTRODUCTION

Deleted: ;

My reading of the ACA-401D period one (1) coursepack allows me to test my technical academic writing ability visa vis the expectation by Euclid University. The course also serves as a stimulant to remind my graduate studies after long years.

Deleted: courserepack

Deleted: EUCLID u

The comprehensive description of the basics of academic writing is a valuable tool that can guide and support the successful completion of the program. The coursepack provides me with the essential tools to succeed in a doctoral course. It helps me engage with competence in a genuine and respectable academic dialogue in my research paper writing. As this is an online program, written communication plays a significant role in clear communication with my course instructor.

Deleted:

2) INTERNATIONAL ACADEMIES PROFESSIONAL PAPER WRITING

Formatted: Justified

Deleted: ;

The ACA-401D period one coursepack has nine chapters with 59 pages. The course pack focuses on the basic process of academic essay writing; it started by giving

Deleted: SEIFU TADESSE

information on the recommended citation for the course pack, which helps to reference the coursepack; [in-text](#), [reference list](#), [footnote](#), and [bibliography](#) (EUCLID 2021, 1-4). The coursepack includes a detailed table of content arranged in main and subtopics.

Deleted: l

Deleted: T

Deleted: R

Deleted: L

Deleted: B

Deleted: cusepack

Deleted: w

Deleted: (EUCLID 2021, 1).

Deleted: Tumbes

Deleted: (EUCLID 2021,14-16)

Deleted: EUCLID

Deleted: u

Deleted: (EUCLID 2021, 23-36).

Deleted: pack

Deleted: defining

The [coursepack](#) for the period started with introductory instruction; “[Essay Writing: The Basics](#) by University of New South Wales (UNSW), Australia.” Defined what plagiarism means with some examples and discussed how to avoid it (EUCLID 2021, 5). Some rules of [thumb](#) for better writing, and how to consult the literature review and style guide (EUCLID 2021, 17-22). Provide advice on the grammar and style from the [Euclid University](#) perspective. America and British English usage described. CMS crib sheet by Dr. Abel Scribe, Ph.D., represent one of the significant styles described to write a different type of EUCLID. The coursepack also includes on [video](#) with the instruction how to use the style guide in the response paper. The major topics included in the coursepack are defining the thesis, [defining](#), and understanding study questions, planning the thesis writing and organizing idea, style guide, and difference between American and British English languages and usage.

3) ESSAY WRITING: THE BASIC.

The first part of the ACA-401D period one [coursepack](#) describes how to start essay writing with the essential steps, organizing ideas and constructing initial plan, researching the topic, note-taking, writing an essay, referencing, and editing addressed in this section. The coursepack described the purpose of evidence as “Academic essay writing aims to persuade readers of an idea based on evidence” (EUCLID 2021, 1). The doctoral course is mainly about researching and writing, and this part of the material is fundamental and relevant to the study.

Communication, specifically digital communication, is becoming an essential part of our life. Learning how to communicate our idea clearly with others in another part of the world has paramount importance, especially in academic written communication. In my previous experience, I have applied some of the points discussed in this part of the paper, such as preparing an outline before writing progress and survey report, referencing, reading, and editing. Moreover, the essay writing part of the coursepack reminds me to give more attention to these golden rules that help me write an excellent academic paper. I refresh my long year writing experience.

The material added value to my understanding of these basic principles, which are the cornerstone for academic writing; I believe that understanding these basics of writing principles is foundation for my long journey for doctoral study and thesis writing. I recommend that students to invest time in this part as it is the basis for future essays writing.

4) ORGANIZING YOUR IDEA: ESSAY PLANNING

Deleted: -

The course paper describes the importance of initial planning and organizing idea that helps or guide the research and structure our essay logically. It also clarifies that the

Deleted: SEIFU TADESSE

initial plan could be adjusted or changed as we [read](#), and our ideas developed more and as we researched further. The adjustment or re-organizing of the essay can be inevitable as there could be an emerging idea as we read further, requiring us to adjust the plan (EUCLID 2021, 2). Planning essay writing is a crucial idea applied in my graduate and professional writing. It is an essential tip for a huge writing assignment in front of me as a doctoral student. Planning and organizing our writing [are](#) vital in academic writing and can also be applied in our professional writing purposes.

Deleted: read

Deleted: is

Organizing ideas and planning an essay is the necessary experience that gave me a direction on what to read and write. Furthermore, organizing and planning an essay writing from the outset is a precious tip that can help to re-organize me before I commence writing. Planning and organizing idea [are](#) the standard student need to follow as part of their academic writing.

Deleted: is

5) PLAGIARISM

Deleted: ;

Issues of plagiarism are a severe offense in academic writing. A considerable part of this section provided the caveat and methods for avoiding the practice with substantial focus and gave practical consideration for citations and paraphrasing. However, offered an alternative, I can paraphrase, reiterate the ideas in my own words that do not excessively look like the original quotation (EUCLID 2021, 3). Another emphasis is that even if the direct quotes are helpful for accuracy, it is good to minimize overuse (EUCLID 2021, 13).

The course pack provided me with adequate information on the importance of citations and how to acknowledge the work or ideas of another author. Equipping the student from the outset how to avoid plagiarism (the severe offense of academic writing) is very relevant and road map and for future writing.

In my long-year career, I witnessed that plagiarism has been a common problem in non-academic writing. Cut and paste is a common practice in business writing. I would suggest that these regulations be adaptable in all forms of writing.

The examples given on citation, referencing, and quotation gave me a practical insight into applying the styles. This section gives me essential and applicable information for doctoral writing. It is a vital tool that can be used in considerable writing ahead of me.

6) STYLE GUIDE

Deleted: ;

The style guide applies to all forms of writing (academic and business or journalism) (EUCLID 2021, 24-26). EUCLID recommended the Chicago Rule [of Style](#) (Turabian) and described that using other internationally recognized styles is also acceptable. Another essential tip addressed in the coursepack is the use of the American vs. British language, the recommendation by [Euclid University](#) to use American English (EUCLID 2021, 24-25). As we will research massive sources for our doctoral academic writing, it is crucial to use a consistent style guide and form of language recommended by the university.

Formatted: Indent: First line: 1.27 cm, Space After: 12 pt

Deleted: EUCLID u

Deleted: SEIFU TADESSE

The idea of using a style guide is related to the course. I used the [American Psychological Association \(APA\)](#) style for my master's writing and did not use the [Turabian](#) style before. It is good that EUCLID recommended using both techniques, and this will give me an option to either of them as appropriate.

Deleted: ¶

Commented [GK3]: Always define acronyms and abbreviations at the point of first use.

Deleted: Turbine

As stated in the coursepacks, the purpose of using the style guide is to maintain consistency and coherence in my writing style throughout the [document and](#) using a style guide can add value to our academic writing (EUCLID 2021, 24-26).

Formatted: Indent: First line: 1.27 cm, Space After: 12 pt

Deleted: document, and

Formatted: English (US)

7) RULES OF THUMBS FOR ACADEMIC WRITING.

Section three of the ACA-401 coursepack discussed some rules of thumb critical for academic writing. The papers describe how to write the essay, the importance of staying focused, how to write, how to avoid dull and clumsy paper, the importance of creating evidence and how to quote a passage, how to take the views seriously you are discussing, and [emphasis no to plagiarize](#) (EUCLID 2021 14-16). This part of the course pack described the principles and methods with practical case stories which can make the understanding strong and live.

Deleted: also

The coursepack provided practical guides relevant to the course and the forthcoming writing. It complements the necessary procedure and principles discussed in the previous section of the response paper. In the real world, professional writers are not worried about rules and assume that it is ok to deliver the right message to the reader. For me applying appropriate rules of thumb in all forms of writing, specifically in academic writing, is crucial for better writing; it can enhance the confidence for the readers to believe the information provided and helps to understand the message we want to convey quickly.

I have been trying to apply these principles in my previous experience in professional and graduate paper writing. It reminds me of my research course and lecture, which has emphasized these rules of thumb; however, when it comes to reality, I am not confident that I have applied these rules in my professional writing, and it was a missed opportunity. I must use all forms (academic and professional) of writing in my future career.

CONCLUSION

Deleted: ¶

The ACA-401/ACA-40D [coursepack for](#) period one and video packs gave me an excellent opportunity to gain a practical guide regarding academic writing. The coursepack is also a good tool beyond academic writing, and I can use it for professional writing in my future career.

Deleted: C

As a doctoral student, it helps me gain essential writing skills and refresh what I know in my previous experience in writing. It is a good starting point for my journey to complete the course and write a thesis. Moreover, it is also a more rewarding tool for my future professional writing. It also gave me a concrete insight into researching, organizing,

and writing my paper and the rules and guides I need to follow in academic writing. Moving forward, I will make my best effort to follow the instructions and regulations, base myself on correct facts and evidence, and avoid personal bias and emotions.

REFERENCE

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, 3rd ed. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui: Euclid University.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.

Deleted: SEIFU TADESSE

Deleted: emotional feelings

Deleted: Note: As per the Grammarly plagiarism check the response paper is rated as 100% original.

Deleted: ¶

Deleted: :

Formatted: RP Title, None, Don't keep with next, Don't keep lines together, Tab stops: Not at 1.75 cm

Formatted: Font: Italic

Deleted: EUCLID